

THE IMPORTANCE OF HABITS IN PROMOTING STUDENTS' INDEPENDENT LEARNING AND EDUCATION

NURALIYEVA MUYASSAR

TURGUNOVA HANIFA

MASHRAPOV QUVONCHBEK

**Mathematical teachers of Vocational School No. 2, Namangan District,
Namangan Region.**

Annotation: The coefficient of habits necessary for independent learning among students, improving teaching methods and control and results through the program.

Key words: Growth and decline coefficient, artificial intelligence, tomato method, focus-to-do, airplane mode, atom, habits.

Every student has their own study period. Homework is always a problem. It makes them bored. It always reduces the motivation to do homework. It makes the next day's lessons better causes him not to do the tasks. Repeated occurrence of this situation makes him lose his enthusiasm and interests. There is no need to be stressed or nervous for this, it is enough if you have a ready helper phone for you.

It is impossible to imagine learning modern knowledge without mathematics. Why? Because it will be difficult to achieve results without time control, not wasting time, and a properly structured daily list of tasks and lessons. Children 1 - 2. Instead of studying for hours, playing games without sleeping for hours will waste the hours, eyesight and nerves needed for the future. An increase of at least 1% every day will lead to an increase of 37.8 times by the end of the year.

When it is the 1st year

$$\left(1 + \frac{1\%}{100\%}\right)^{365 \text{ days}} = 37.7834343329$$

When in the 2nd year

$$\left(1 + \frac{1\%}{100\%}\right)^{730 \text{ days}} = 1427.58790999$$

When in the 3rd year

$$\left(1 + \frac{1\%}{100\%}\right)^{1095 \text{ days}} = 53939.1740514$$

And after the 4th year

$$\left(1 + \frac{1\%}{100\%}\right)^{1460 \text{ days}} = 2038007.24074 = 2 \text{mln } 38 \text{ ming } 7$$

... ..

and in the nth year

$$\left(1 + \frac{1\%}{100\%}\right)^{n \cdot 365 \text{ days}} = (37.7834343329)^{n \text{ years}}$$

This shows that our change O is directly proportional to the time T (O~T).
what will happen if it decreases: when it is 1st year

$$\left(1 - \frac{1\%}{100\%}\right)^{365 \text{ days}} = 0.02551796445$$

When in the 2nd year

$$\left(1 - \frac{1\%}{100\%}\right)^{730 \text{ days}} = 0.0006511665$$

In the 3rd year

$$\left(1 - \frac{1\%}{100\%}\right)^{1095 \text{ days}} = 0.00001661644$$

And after the 4th year

$$\left(1 - \frac{1\%}{100\%}\right)^{1460 \text{ days}} = 0,00000004.240$$

... ..

and in the nth year

$$\left(1 - \frac{1\%}{100\%}\right)^{n*365k \text{ days}} = (0.99)^n \text{ years}$$

The above decrements show that you can see that the end of each daily decrement approaches zero. That is, if you constantly repeat a useful habit, you grow, and its decrement turns it into zero.

Habits are a daily, monthly, annual, recurring force that affects the knowledge and behavior that adorns your life. For example, if we take athletes who play sports, they do not form special habits, starting from every meal before the competition, to doing daily exercises. the result will be less. Today, the habit of not studying is increasing among students, which prevents them from working on themselves. And the habit of not studying every day can turn into a tragedy. We guide students from easy to difficult daily tasks according to their needs and interests. It is enough to ask the teacher of the first turn where he is lacking, to turn on the airplane mode on the phone. If not from the teacher, then it is enough to look for atomic habits from artificial intelligence and understand it at least once. and the necessary program for time control is FOCUS-TO-DO program.

CONCLUSION

The above program helps students to show 80% results by working 20%. It

helps them to form their consciousness, strengthen their memory, concentrate, and perform many tasks in 25 minutes. Always it helps to form the ability and habit of independent learning.

LIST OF REFERENCES.

1. Atomic Habits by James Clear
2. Atom odatlar James Clear. (Jeyms Klir)
3. Rich Dad Poor Dad: What the Rich Teach Their Kids About Money That the Poor and Middle Class Do Not! Mass Market Paperback – April 11, 2017
4. <https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.superelement.pomodoro>
5. <https://apps.apple.com/us/app/focus-to-do-pomodoro-tasks/id1258530160?mt=12>